
Social Media Addiction Among Senior High School Learners

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Abstract

Social media has been widely accessible to all in the advent of new technology, specifically in mobile devices. Many researchers are studying related to social media's effects on the different walks and aspects of life. The study aims at profiling and identifying the extent of social media addiction of senior high school students of Butuan City School of Arts and Trades - Philippines, in January 2020. The study was administered to 513 senior high students with social media accounts. It was found out that 294 out of 513 are social media addicts and mostly use Facebook. The majority of social media addicts are female, grade 12 students, and 18 years of age.

Keywords: Social Media Addiction; Senior High School; Facebook Addiction Scale.

1. Introduction

Social media has become pervasive, impacting our society's social fabric and changing the nature of social relationships, especially young people. Social media are websites and applications that enable them to create and share content or participate in social networking benefiting their users [1]. However, students' excessive use of social media tools has led to debate over whether or not it has changed the very shape and structure of students' social behavior and academic practices. Thus, it has caused leading educators to redefine their understanding of interpersonal communication and study dynamics [2]. All over the world, young individuals with age below 24 have the highest number of social media users, according to the latest report of the website DataReportal on the 2019 Global Digital Report [3].

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Based on the age range, most of these users belonged to junior and senior high school students. The result sounds alarming to all schools worldwide if these numbers are negatively correlated to school performance. In the same report, the country has the most significant number of users in the Philippines. In the Philippines, 46% of its 107 million population are active social media users with an average browsing time of 10 hours and 2 minutes per day [4]. Daily, Filipinos are browsing primarily on social media platforms such as Youtube and Facebook. According to [3], a big crack of social media users accesses the internet through mobile devices. The population's share using mobile phones was around 65.3 % and forecasted to grow to about 70 percent in 2020 [5]. Attributed to the increase in social media use among Filipino students is the proliferation of cheap mobile phones [6]. Due to the decrease in mobile phones' price with browsing capabilities, parents even in the lower class can now afford to provide for their children. Though parents' intentions are clean in providing phones to their children, yet one cannot assure that students appropriately execute these intentions. The Department of Education (DepEd) of the Philippines is aware of this problem that most of our schools face and made regulations on mobile devices. As early as 1999, the department had already regulated the phone's use during class hours as stipulated in DECS order number 70 in 1999 and 26 in 2000. Though social media before was not yet developed, the purpose of the department's orders transcends beyond ages, and that is to help the learners focus more on their lessons and not on their cellphones. The department is afraid that learner's use of mobile devices will lead to more disturbing effects such as addiction. Excessive use of phones and other electronic gadgets to browse social media over a long period can be one indicator of social media addiction. As defined by Andressean [7], social media addiction is "being overly concerned about Social Networking Sites (SNSs), to be driven by a strong motivation to log on to or use SNSs, and to devote so much time and effort to SNSs that it impairs other social activities, studies/job, interpersonal relationships, and/or psychological health and well-being." Based on the definition given above, one cannot tell addiction unless we scale its different aspects. Teachers in Butuan City School of Arts and Trade, like any other schools, are making much effort in educating their learners. Even though all the efforts, teachers seem to feel disappointed with their performance due to many distractions. Most of the educators pinpoint addiction to social media as the main reason why students are performing low. Assessing student's addiction levels can be reliable if done through proper tools. Knowing students' level of addiction will be of great help in employing intervention to help students. Given that need, the research is urged to conduct this research.

2. Statement of the problem

This research study aimed to answer the following questions:

- What is the demographic profile of social media users of Butuan City School of Arts and Trade?
 - Age;
 - Gender; and
 - Grade Level
- What do senior high school students use the typical social networking sites?
- What is the level of social media addiction of Butuan City School of Arts and Trades senior high school students?
- What is the profile of social media addicts?

3. Literature Review

3.1 Social Media/ Social Networking Sites

Social media consists of online technologies, practicing activities, or societies that people use to generate content and share thoughts, visions, experiences, and viewpoints. Social networking is known as the alliance of individuals into a specific set of potential groups or subdivisions. Social networking allows individuals to express their thoughts to other users. Social networking is the leader in promoting digital journalism [8]—the social network used for several purposes like promoting or distributing news contents worldwide. Social networking sites and Facebook socializing via the internet have become an increasingly important part of young adult life [9]. Most of the high schools, colleges, and universities connected by the internet encompass individuals looking forward to mingling with other individuals with the same point of interest, gathering and sharing knowledge and first-hand information. Social networking websites act like an online society of users who is familiar with the internet. Social networks are developed with more advanced features after the year 2003. Since Facebook holds the most significant number of active users, it became referred to by the name social network.

3.2 Social Media Addiction

To get a better understanding of Social Networking Site (SNS), the explanation of Kuss and Griffiths [10] is applicable; SNS are virtual communities where users can create individual public profiles, interact with real-life friends, and meet other people based on shared interests on several means like desktops and mobile devices. Thus, the main difference between the internet and SNS is the interaction principle with others, where internet use also consists of online communication [11], only to a minor degree with fewer features. Therefore, it is assumed that SNS are more susceptible to addiction behavior because of the constant interaction with others by several means. From an SNS addiction perspective, symptoms like conflict, withdrawal, and behavioral salience are consistent with internet addiction [12,13]. Still, it is not possible to suggest that users with internet addiction also have an SNS addiction, simply because SNS's are a specific part of the internet with unique features. For SNS addiction, there are also consequences involved, namely, loneliness [14], less involvement in real-life communities, [15] worse academic performance [16], and relational problems [17].

3.3 Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale

Addiction cannot be predicted by just mere observation. Proper and more accurate estimation can only achieve through proper scale or tool. In January 2011, 423 students - 227 women and 196 men - participated in tests for the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale. The scale can facilitate treatment research and clinical assessment and can be used to estimate Facebook addiction prevalence in the general population worldwide [7]. The Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale has been developed at the Faculty of Psychology, the University of Bergen, in collaboration with the Bergen Clinics Foundation, Norway. The researchers also work with instruments measuring other addictions, such as the recently introduced Bergen Work Addiction Scale [7]. The scale consists of 18 items, three reflecting each of the six core elements of addiction (salience, mood, modification,

tolerance, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse) (Ibid). BFAS developers suggested a polythetic scoring scheme was used to determine the Facebook addicts in the sample. This scheme suggests those who answer three or above on at least four of the six items are Facebook addicts [18].

3.4 Social Media Use of Students

Today's students (which consist of Baby Boomers, Generation Xers, and Millennials) are exposed to all types of technologies in many aspects of their lives [19]. Daily they use desktop computers, laptops, e-readers, tablets, and cell phones to engage in social networking actively, text messaging, blogging, and similar activities. Social networking sites such as Facebook and MySpace have been subject to much recent debate within the educational community. While growing numbers of educators celebrate social networking's potential to reengage learners with their studies, others fear that such applications compromise and disrupt young people's engagement with "traditional" education provision [20].

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive survey design. Descriptive-survey research uses surveys to gather data about varying subjects. This data aims to know the extent to which different conditions can be obtained among these subjects. This design fits the research study since it wants to know about social media addiction among the respondents.

4.2 The Population

Table 1: The population by grade level and specialization

GRADE	MAJOR	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
GRADE 11	ABM	13	23	36
	GAS	42	48	90
	HUMSS	20	29	49
	STEM	32	31	63
	AUTO	51	0	51
	EIM	34	0	34
	EPAS	38	3	41
	FS	10	24	34
GRADE 12	ABM	10	40	50
	GAS	33	62	95
	HUMSS	29	33	62
	STEM	30	21	51
	AUTO	79	0	79
	EIM	44	2	46
	EPAS	47	7	54
	FS	9	36	45
TOTAL		521	359	880

The school has 880 senior high school students during the school year 2019-2020. These students are enrolled

either in Academic Track or Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL)Track. The academic track comprised of Accountancy and Business Management (ABM), Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), General Academic Strand (GAS), and Humanities and Social Science (HUMSS). TVL, on the other hand, students can choose from Automotive Servicing (AUTO), Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM), Electronic Products Assembly and Services (EPAS), and Food Services (EPAS).

4.3 The Sample

The study employed purposive sampling. All Senior High School students of Butuan City School of Arts and Trade with social media account during the school year 2019-2020 were considered respondents. They were contacted through the help of their class advisers. With the students' consent and their parents, 513 (58.3 %) of 880 SHS students agreed to join the survey. All those who agreed to join the survey need to have an active social media account for at least one year.

4.4 Research Instrument

The study adopted a tested questionnaire to determine the students' social media addiction level called the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS) [7]. This scale comprised 18 items, three for each of the six core features of addiction: salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse. Each item is scored on a 5-point scale using anchors of 1: Very rarely and 5: Very often. Higher As suggested by BFAS developers, the polythetic scoring scheme was used to determine the Facebook addicts in the sample. This scheme suggests those who answer three or above on at least four of the six items are Facebook addicts [18]. Apart from answering the BFAS, the respondents also completed a profile section to determine their age, year level, type of social media users, and academic performance.

4.5 Data Collection

The researcher used an adapted tool known as Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale BFAS by [7]. BFAS was already administered in the Philippines to students of Siliman University [21]. The tool was devised to assess the Facebook addiction level among social media patrons. Additional sections were included to collect the demographic profile of the respondents. The questionnaires were administered via Google forms online, making the process paperless. All students with access to the internet were the significant respondents. A link to the questionnaire was also created for easy access and sharing. To ensure greater participation amongst respondents, the researcher asked the classroom adviser assistance by posting the link to their respected group chats or page. After two weeks of being available online, the researcher officially closed the survey. As one of the Google Form features, the researcher could export the collection to excel to be treated statistically.

4.6 Data Analysis

The study used descriptive statistics in obtaining answers to the questions.

4.7 Limitations

The study focused only on senior high school students of Butuan City School of Arts and Trades, Butuan City, Philippines, with social media accounts during the second semester of the school year 2019-2020. The study will only describe the social media addiction among senior high school students. The result will reflect the school's condition and should not be used to generalized the current situation of all the schools in the Philippines.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Profile of Respondents

The study was conducted on senior high school students of Butuan City School of Arts and Trades, Butuan City Philippines, who have access to social media during the second semester of 2019-2020. The total number of respondents is 513, which males mainly dominate. The world report confirms the data gathered that males dominate females in the total number of Facebook users worldwide [3]. Grade 12 students with 372 participants have the most significant number of social media users than the 141 users in grade 11. These Grade 12 students are mostly 18 years of age. Based on the report "Digital 2019: Global Digital Overview," the highest number of social media users are primarily in the 18-25 age group. In Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, the pyramid's higher tiers are founded upon love, belongingness, self-esteem, and self-actualization, which all can be satisfied with social media use. Any individual, including students, used social media to satisfy their needs [22]. Though social media promote collaboration and communication addiction, this might also pose a danger to any person engaged too much [23].

Table 2: Demographic Profile of Respondents

		N	%
Age	16	39	8%
	17	159	31%
	18	204	40%
	19	84	16%
	20	9	2%
	21	3	1%
	22	9	2%
	23	3	1%
	26	3	1%
	Gender	Male	228
Female		285	44%
Grade Level	Grade 11	141	27%
	Grade 12	372	73%

5.2 Social Networking Sites

The social networking site SNSs used mainly by the respondents is Facebook. Facebook users comprise 88% of the total respondents, way too high than the second Youtube (6%). Twitter has the least number of patrons, which only tallied 6 out of 513 users or 1%. From a global perspective, Facebook still ranks as one of the fast-growing social networking sites based on the total number of unique users. However, it was observed to have grown slightly off compared to another SNSs last year [3]. Facebook still holds strong with its 2.54 billion users [5]. Based on studies, Facebook became popular due to its attractive self-gratification feature by sharing content and insights online [24].

Table 3: Common Social Networking Site

	N	%
Facebook	450	88%
Twitter	6	1%
Instagram	9	2%
Youtube	33	6%
Others	15	3%

5.3 Social Media Addiction

The research administers an adopted survey questionnaire known as Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS) to 513 respondents to identify social media addiction. BFAS suggests that there is an addiction when there are at least four of the six items scored as "often" or "very often" [7]. Based on the data gathered, 57% or 294 out of 513 of the total respondents are Facebook or social media addicts. Though the aggregate average of social media addiction is not that high, the number of social media addicts among SHS students is high. The result implies in every 100 students, 57 of them are social media addicts. Moreover, Facebook addicts are rated almost equally in all categories of BFAS. On a closer look, Salience, Tolerance, and Mood modification rank higher compared with other categories. High tolerance in BFAS means that most Facebook addicts think most of the time engaging in social media when doing other tasks. Tolerance denotes that most of the identified social media addicts tolerate social media use and often take more time. High in mood modification signifies that students indulged in social media addiction have modified or changed their mood. According to Cabral [25], most young users of social media are propelled by their need to maintain relationships with peers. He added that most social media addicts scored high in three components, tolerance, salience, and relapse of the BFAS.

Table 4: Social Media Addiction

	N	%
Addicts	294	57%
Non-Addicts	219	43%

5.4 Profile of Social Media Addicts

The majority of social media addicts are 18 years old, female, and grade 12 students. The outcome is in support of the world report of social media users in 2019. In support of the study of MPh in 2015, the age of social media addicts is in the spectrum of SHS students. Moreover, female accounts the most significant number of social media addicts. The data is similar to the study of Biolcati, Mancini, and Mugheddu [26]. Based on the study of Parkins [27], women are found to be a more expressive gender. The women's expressiveness can all be traced back to society, which creates this stereotype. Social media – a very accessible tool and easy to use – offers women of all ages a very fertile soil to express their feelings and emotions. Gard and company [28] also added that women have more guts to express themselves over males, especially in public areas like social media. However, despite this claim, social media offers anonymity to its users, which can hide basic information like the user's true gender. They emphasize that social media can offer a perfect camouflage for expressive males if this is the case.

Table 5: Profile of Social Media Addicts

		N	%
Age	16	18	6%
	17	93	32%
	18	126	43%
	19	42	14%
	20	3	1%
	21	0	0%
	22	6	2%
	23	3	1%
	26	3	1%
Gender	Male	129	44%
	Female	165	56%
Grade Level	Grade 11	54	18%
	Grade 12	240	82%

6. Conclusion

After gathering all the data and doing the analysis, the researcher concludes that social media addiction in senior high students of Butuan City School of Arts and Trades is a real thing. The researcher felt the urgency to focus on adolescent students since more of this group is experiencing social media addiction. The school needs to make necessary interventions to help students, teachers, and parents know about social media's positive use and help students channel this addiction to good use.

7. Recommendations

The author recommends further studying the nature of students' social media addiction to explain the reason for their addiction. The case study is also advised to make a realistic view of students' lives considered social media

addicts. Furthermore, the research would like to recommend studies that would link social addiction to student's performance.

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